

Existence, uniqueness and monotonicity of positive solutions for hybrid fractional integro-differential equations

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Received: 15 Nov 2020

Accepted: 30 Nov 2020

Published Online: 08 Dec 2020

Abstract: In this paper, we study the existence, uniqueness and monotonicity of positive solutions of hybrid nonlinear fractional integro-differential equations by the method of upper and lower solutions and using the Dhage and Banach fixed point theorems. Two examples of the obtained results are given.

Key words: Fractional integro-differential equations, fixed point theorems, existence, positivity, monotonicity.

1. Introduction

The concept of fractional calculus is a generalization of the ordinary differentiation and integration to arbitrary non integer order. Fractional differential equations with and without delay arise from a variety of applications including in various fields of science and engineering such as applied sciences, physics, chemistry, biology, medicine, etc. In particular, problems concerning qualitative analysis of linear and nonlinear fractional differential equations with and without delay have received the attention of many authors, see [1]–[13], [15]–[33] and the references therein.

Hybrid differential equations arise from a variety of different areas of applied mathematics and physics, e.g., in the deflection of a curved beam having a constant or varying cross section, a three-layer beam, electromagnetic waves or gravity driven flows and so on [2, 3, 11, 13, 14, 33].

Dhage and Lakshmikantham [14] discussed the existence of solutions for the following first-order hybrid differential equation

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{x(t)}{g(t, x(t))} \right) = f(t, x(t)) \text{ a.e. } t \in [t_0, t_0 + T], \\ x(t_0) = x_0 \in \mathbb{R}, \end{cases}$$

where $t_0, T \in \mathbb{R}$ with $T > 0$, $g : [t_0, t_0 + T] \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$ and $f : [t_0, t_0 + T] \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are continuous functions. By using the fixed point theorem in Banach algebra, the authors obtained the existence results.

Let $\mathfrak{J} = [0, \mathfrak{a}]$ be a closed and bounded interval of the real line \mathbb{R} for some $\mathfrak{a} \in \mathbb{R}$ with $\mathfrak{a} > 0$. The hybrid

fractional differential equation

$$\begin{cases} D^\alpha \left(\frac{x(t)}{g(t, x(t))} \right) = f(t, x(t)) \text{ a.e. } t \in \mathfrak{J}, \\ x(0) = 0, \end{cases}$$

has been investigated in [33], where D^α is the Riemann-Liouville fractional derivative of order $0 < \alpha < 1$, $g : \mathfrak{J} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$ and $f : \mathfrak{J} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are continuous functions. By employing the fixed point theorem in Banach algebra, the authors obtained the existence of a solution.

Ardjouni and Djoudi [5] studied the existence and approximation of the solutions of the following hybrid nonlinear fractional integro-differential equation

$$\begin{cases} {}^C D^\alpha \left(\frac{x(t)}{p(t) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_0^t (t-s)^{\beta-1} g(s, x(s)) ds} \right) = f(t, x(t)), t \in \mathfrak{J}, \\ x(0) = p(0)\theta, \end{cases}$$

where ${}^C D^\alpha$ is the Caputo fractional derivative of order $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, $0 < \beta \leq 1$, $\theta \in \mathbb{R}$, $p : \mathfrak{J} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $g, f : \mathfrak{J} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are continuous functions. By using the Dhage iteration principle, the authors obtained the existence and approximation of solutions.

Let $J = [t_0, T]$. Matar [28] investigated the existence, uniqueness and monotonicity of positive solutions for the following hybrid fractional differential equation

$$\begin{cases} {}^C D_{t_0}^\alpha \left(\frac{x(t)}{g(t, x(t))} \right) = f(t, x(t)), t \in J, \\ x(t_0) = \theta \geq 0, \end{cases}$$

where ${}^C D_{t_0}^\alpha$ is the Caputo fractional derivative of order $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, $f : J \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $g : J \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$ are given continuous functions such that $g(t_0, \theta) = \lambda > 0$. By using the method of the upper and lower solutions and the Dhage and Banach fixed point theorems, the author obtained the existence, uniqueness and monotonicity of a positive solution.

Inspired and motivated by the works mentioned above and some recent studies on hybrid fractional differential equations, we consider the existence, uniqueness and monotonicity of positive solutions for the following hybrid nonlinear fractional integro-differential equation

$$\begin{cases} {}^C D_{t_0}^\alpha \left(\frac{x(t)}{p(t) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\beta-1} g(s, x(s)) ds} \right) = f(t, x(t)), t \in J, \\ x(t_0) = p(t_0)\theta \geq 0, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $0 < \alpha, \beta \leq 1$, $f, g : J \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $p : J \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are given continuous functions. To show the existence, uniqueness and monotonicity of positive solutions, we transform (1) into an integral equation and then by the method of upper and lower solutions and use Dhage and Banach fixed point theorems.

2. Preliminaries

In this section we present some basic definitions, lemmas and theorems which will be used in this paper. For more details, see [14, 23, 31].

Let $X = C(J)$ be the Banach space of all real-valued continuous functions defined on the compact interval J , endowed with the maximum norm. Define the subset $\mathcal{C}_\theta = \{x \in X : x(t) \geq p(t_0)\theta, t \in J\}$ of X .

Definition 2.1 ([23]). The fractional integral of order $\alpha > 0$ for a continuous function $x : [t_0, +\infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined as

$$I_{t_0}^\alpha x(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} x(s) ds.$$

Definition 2.2 ([23]). The Caputo fractional derivative of order $\alpha > 0$ for a continuous function $x : [t_0, +\infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined as

$${}^C D_{t_0}^\alpha x(t) = I_{t_0}^{n-\alpha} x^{(n)}(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{n-\alpha-1} x^{(n)}(s) ds,$$

where $n = [\alpha] + 1$.

Lemma 2.1 ([23]). Let $\alpha > 0$ and $x \in C^{n-1}[t_0, +\infty)$ and $x^{(n)}$ exists almost everywhere on any bounded interval of \mathbb{R}^+ . Then

$$(I_{t_0}^{\alpha C} D_{t_0}^\alpha x)(t) = x(t) - \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{x^{(k)}(t_0)}{k!} t^k.$$

In particular, when $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, $(I_{t_0}^{\alpha C} D_{t_0}^\alpha x)(t) = x(t) - x(t_0)$.

Definition 2.3. For any $x \in [a, b] \subset \mathbb{R}^+$, we define the upper-control function by

$$U(t, x) = \sup \{f(t, s) : a \leq s \leq x\},$$

and the lower-control function by

$$L(t, x) = \inf \{f(t, s) : x \leq s \leq b\}.$$

It is obvious that these functions are non-decreasing on $[a, b]$, i.e.

$$L(t, x) \leq f(t, x) \leq U(t, x), \quad t \in J.$$

Definition 2.4. A function $x \in X$ is positive bounded below if $x \in \mathcal{C}_\theta$. In particular, we call x as nonnegative function if $p(t_0)\theta = 0$ and positive function if $p(t_0)\theta > 0$.

The following fixed point theorem due to Dhage [14] is essential tool for the proof of the first result.

Theorem 2.1 ([14]). Let S be a nonempty bounded closed convex subset of a Banach algebra X . Let $\mathcal{B} : S \rightarrow X$ and $\mathcal{A} : S \rightarrow X$ be two operators such that

- i) \mathcal{A} is Lipschitz with a Lipschitz constant σ ,
- ii) \mathcal{B} is completely continuous,
- iii) $\mathcal{A}x\mathcal{B}y \in S$ for all $x, y \in S$.

Then the product operator equation

$$\mathcal{A}x\mathcal{B}x = x,$$

has a solution, whenever $\sigma M < 1$, where $M = \sup \{\|\mathcal{B}x\| : x \in S\}$.

3. Existence of positive solutions

In this section, we will discuss the existence of positive solutions for (1). We introduce the following conditions

(H1) For $t \in J$ and $x \in X$, we have

$$p(t) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\beta-1} g(s, x(s)) ds > 0,$$

and

$$\theta + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} f(s, x(s)) ds \geq 0.$$

(H2) Let $x^*, x_* \in \mathcal{C}_\theta$, such that $x_*(t_0) = x^*(t_0) = p(t_0)\theta$ and $p(t_0)\theta \leq x_*(t) \leq x^*(t) \leq b$, $t \in J$.

Moreover,

$$\begin{cases} {}^C D_{t_0}^\alpha \left(\frac{x^*(t)}{p(t) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\beta-1} g(s, x^*(s)) ds} \right) \geq U(t, x^*(t)), \\ {}^C D_{t_0}^\alpha \left(\frac{x_*(t)}{p(t) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\beta-1} g(s, x_*(s)) ds} \right) \leq L(t, x_*(t)), \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

for any $t \in J$.

(H3) Let g be monotonic non-decreasing with respect to x and there exists $L_g > 0$ such that

$$|g(t, x) - g(t, y)| \leq L_g |x - y|, \quad t \in J, \quad x, y \in \mathbb{R},$$

where

$$0 < L_g \frac{(T-t_0)^\beta}{\Gamma(\beta+1)} \left(|\theta| + \frac{c_f (T-t_0)^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \right) < 1.$$

(H4) There exists $L_f > 0$ such that

$$|f(t, x) - f(t, y)| \leq L_f |x - y|, \quad t \in J, \quad x, y \in \mathbb{R}.$$

The functions x^* and x_* are respectively called the pair of upper and lower solutions for (1).

From Lemma 2.1, we deduce the following lemma.

Lemma 3.1. Assume that $\frac{x}{h}$ is differentiable on J . Then the equation

$$\begin{cases} {}^C D_{t_0}^\alpha \left(\frac{x(t)}{h(t)} \right) = f(t, x(t)), \quad t \in J, \\ x(t_0) = p(t_0)\theta, \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

is equivalent to

$$x(t) = h(t) \left(\theta + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} f(s, x(s)) ds \right), \quad t \in J. \quad (4)$$

By the previous lemma, (1) is equivalent to

$$x(t) = \left(p(t) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\beta-1} g(s, x(s)) ds \right) \left(\theta + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} f(s, x(s)) ds \right), \quad t \in J.$$

Hence, according to the Dhage fixed point theorem 2.1, we define the operators $\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B} : \mathcal{C}_\theta \rightarrow \mathcal{C}_\theta$ by

$$(\mathcal{A}x)(t) = p(t) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\beta-1} g(s, x(s)) ds, \quad (5)$$

and

$$(\mathcal{B}x)(t) = \theta + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} f(s, x(s)) ds, \quad (6)$$

for $t \in J$.

Theorem 3.1. *Assume that (H1) – (H3) are satisfied, then the problem (1) has at last one positive bounded below solution $x \in \mathcal{C}_\theta$ satisfying $x_*(t) \leq x(t) \leq x^*(t)$, $t \in J$.*

Proof. Let $S = \{x \in \mathcal{C}_\theta : x_*(t) \leq x(t) \leq x^*(t), t \in J\}$, endowed with the norm $\|x\| = \max_{t \in J} |x(t)|$, then for any $x \in S$, we have $\|x\| \leq b$. Hence, S is a convex, bounded and closed subset of \mathcal{C}_θ . Moreover, the continuity of g and f implies the continuity of the operators \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} on S . Now, if $x \in S$ there exists a positive constant c_f such that $\max\{|f(t, x(t))| : (t, x) \in J \times S\} \leq c_f$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} |(\mathcal{B}x)(t)| &= \left| \theta + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} f(s, x(s)) ds \right| \\ &\leq |\theta| + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} |f(s, x(s))| ds \\ &\leq |\theta| + \frac{c_f}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} ds \\ &\leq |\theta| + \frac{c_f (t-t_0)^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\|\mathcal{B}x\| \leq |\theta| + \frac{c_f (T-t_0)^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}.$$

Hence, $\mathcal{B}(S)$ is uniformly bounded. Next, we prove the equicontinuity of \mathcal{B} . Let $x \in S$, then for any $t_1, t_2 \in J$, $t_2 > t_1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &|(\mathcal{B}x)(t_2) - (\mathcal{B}x)(t_1)| \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \left| \int_{t_0}^{t_2} (t_2-s)^{\alpha-1} f(s, x(s)) ds - \int_{t_0}^{t_1} (t_1-s)^{\alpha-1} f(s, x(s)) ds \right| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\int_{t_0}^{t_1} \left((t_1-s)^{\alpha-1} - (t_2-s)^{\alpha-1} \right) |f(s, x(s))| ds + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} (t_2-s)^{\alpha-1} |f(s, x(s))| ds \right) \\ &\leq \frac{c_f}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(\int_{t_0}^{t_1} (t_1-s)^{\alpha-1} - (t_2-s)^{\alpha-1} ds + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} (t_2-s)^{\alpha-1} ds \right) \\ &\leq \frac{c_f}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \left((t_1-t_0)^\alpha - (t_2-t_0)^\alpha + 2(t_2-t_1)^\alpha \right) \\ &\leq \frac{2c_f}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (t_2-t_1)^\alpha. \end{aligned}$$

As $t_1 \rightarrow t_2$ the right-hand side of the previous inequality is independent of x and tends to zero. Therefore, $\mathcal{B}(S)$ is equicontinuous. The Arzela-Ascoli theorem implies that \mathcal{B} is compact. Hence \mathcal{B} is completely continuous.

By hypothesis **(H3)**, for any $x, y \in S$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\mathcal{A}x)(t) - (\mathcal{A}y)(t)| \\
 &= \left| \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\beta-1} g(s, x(s)) ds - \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\beta-1} g(s, y(s)) ds \right| \\
 &\leq \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\beta-1} |g(s, x(s)) - g(s, y(s))| ds \\
 &\leq \frac{L_g}{\Gamma(\beta)} \left(\int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\beta-1} ds \right) \|x - y\| \\
 &\leq \frac{L_g (T - t_0)^\beta}{\Gamma(\beta + 1)} \|x - y\|.
 \end{aligned}$$

Then \mathcal{A} is Lipschitz mapping with Lipschitz constant $\sigma = L_g \frac{(T-t_0)^\beta}{\Gamma(\beta+1)}$, that satisfying $\sigma \sup \{\|\mathcal{B}x\| : x \in S\} < 1$.

We need to prove that $\mathcal{A}x\mathcal{B}y \in S$ for all $x, y \in S$. Indeed, by Definition 2.3 and the hypothesis **(H3)**, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (\mathcal{A}x)(t) (\mathcal{B}y)(t) \\
 &= \left(p(t) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\beta-1} g(s, x(s)) ds \right) \left(\theta + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} f(s, y(s)) ds \right) \\
 &\leq \left(p(t) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\beta-1} g(s, x(s)) ds \right) \left(\theta + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} U(s, y(s)) ds \right) \\
 &\leq \left(p(t) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\beta-1} g(s, x^*(s)) ds \right) \left(\theta + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} U(s, x^*(s)) ds \right) \\
 &\leq x^*(t),
 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (\mathcal{A}x)(t) (\mathcal{B}y)(t) \\
 &\geq \left(p(t) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\beta-1} g(s, x(s)) ds \right) \left(\theta + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} L(s, y(s)) ds \right) \\
 &\geq \left(p(t) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\beta-1} g(s, x_*(s)) ds \right) \left(\theta + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} L(s, x_*(s)) ds \right) \\
 &\geq x_*(t).
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $x_*(t) \leq \mathcal{A}x(t)\mathcal{B}y(t) \leq x^*(t)$, $t \in J$, that is $(\mathcal{A}x\mathcal{B}y)(S) \subseteq S$. According to the Dhage fixed point theorem, the operator equation $\mathcal{A}x\mathcal{B}x = x$ has at last one fixed point $x \in S$. Therefore, the problem (1) has at last one positive bounded below solution $x \in \mathcal{C}_\theta$. \square

Next, we consider many particular cases of the previous theorem.

Corollary 3.1. *Assume that (H3) holds and there exist $k_1, k_2, k_3, k_4 \in X$, such that*

$$k_1(t) \leq g(t, x(t)) \leq k_2(t), \quad (7)$$

and

$$k_3(t) \leq f(t, x(t)) \leq k_4(t). \quad (8)$$

If

$$p(t) + I_{t_0}^\beta k_1(t) > 0, \quad (9)$$

and

$$\theta + I_{t_0}^\alpha k_3(t) \geq 0, \quad (10)$$

then the problem (1) has at least one positive bounded below solution. Moreover

$$\left(p(t) + I_{t_0}^\beta k_1(t) \right) \left(\theta + I_{t_0}^\alpha k_3(t) \right) \leq x(t) \leq \left(p(t) + I_{t_0}^\beta k_2(t) \right) \left(\theta + I_{t_0}^\alpha k_4(t) \right).$$

Proof. By the assumption (8) and the definition of control functions, we have

$$k_3(t) \leq L(t, x(t)) \leq U(t, x(t)) \leq k_4(t),$$

for any $t \in J$. Now, we consider the fractional differential equations

$${}^C D_{t_0}^\alpha \left(\frac{x(t)}{p(t) + I_{t_0}^\beta k_1(t)} \right) = k_3(t), \quad x(t_0) = p(t_0) \theta, \quad (11)$$

and

$${}^C D_{t_0}^\alpha \left(\frac{x(t)}{p(t) + I_{t_0}^\beta k_2(t)} \right) = k_4(t), \quad x(t_0) = p(t_0) \theta. \quad (12)$$

In accordance of Lemma 3.1, the solutions of (11) and (12) are given respectively by

$$x(t) = \left(p(t) + I_{t_0}^\beta k_1(t) \right) \left(\theta + I_{t_0}^\alpha k_3(t) \right),$$

and

$$x(t) = \left(p(t) + I_{t_0}^\beta k_2(t) \right) \left(\theta + I_{t_0}^\alpha k_4(t) \right).$$

Therefore,

$$x(t) = \left(p(t) + I_{t_0}^\beta k_1(t) \right) \left(\theta + I_{t_0}^\alpha k_3(t) \right) \leq \left(p(t) + I_{t_0}^\beta k_1(t) \right) \left(\theta + I_{t_0}^\alpha L(t, x(t)) \right),$$

and

$$x(t) = \left(p(t) + I_{t_0}^\beta k_2(t) \right) \left(\theta + I_{t_0}^\alpha k_4(t) \right) \geq \left(p(t) + I_{t_0}^\beta k_2(t) \right) \left(\theta + I_{t_0}^\alpha U(t, x(t)) \right).$$

One can define the upper and lower solutions as

$$x^*(t) = \left(p(t) + I_{t_0}^\beta k_2(t) \right) \left(\theta + I_{t_0}^\alpha U(t, x^*(t)) \right),$$

and

$$x_*(t) = \left(p(t) + I_{t_0}^\beta k_1(t) \right) \left(\theta + I_{t_0}^\alpha L(t, x_*(t)) \right).$$

Hence by Theorem 3.1, the problem (1) has a positive bounded below solution $x \in \mathcal{C}_\theta$. \square

Corollary 3.2. *Let $k \in X$ and $\varphi \in \mathbb{R}_+$ such that $\varphi < k(t) = \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} f(t, x) < \infty$ for $t \in J$. If **(H3)**, (7) and (9) hold and $\theta \in \mathbb{R}_+$, then the problem (1) has at least one positive bounded below solution. Moreover for $0 < \omega < \varphi$,*

$$\left(p(t) + I_{t_0}^\beta k_1(t)\right) \left(\theta + \frac{(\varphi - \omega)(t - t_0)^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}\right) \leq x(t) \leq \left(p(t) + I_{t_0}^\beta k_2(t)\right) \left(\theta + I_{t_0}^\alpha k(t) + \frac{\omega(t - t_0)^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}\right).$$

Corollary 3.3. *Assume that **(H3)**, (7) and (9) hold, and*

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \theta} \frac{f(t, x)}{x} = \gamma(t),$$

where $\gamma \in X$, $t \in J$. Then there exists a positive bounded below solution of the problem (1).

Corollary 3.4. *Let μ , ν and ξ are real positive numbers such that $\mu \leq f(t, x(t)) \leq \nu x(t) + \xi$, for $t \in J$. If (7), (9) and **(H3)** hold and $\theta \in \mathbb{R}_+$, then the problem (1) has at least one positive bounded below solution. Moreover*

$$\left(p(t) + I_{t_0}^\beta k_1(t)\right) \left(\theta + \frac{\mu(t - t_0)^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}\right) \leq x(t) \leq \left(p(t) + I_{t_0}^\beta k_2(t)\right) \left(\theta + I_{t_0}^\alpha (\nu x(t) + \xi)\right).$$

4. Uniqueness of positive solutions

In this portion, we will demonstrate the uniqueness of the bounded below positive solution of (1) using the Banach contraction mapping principle.

Theorem 4.1. *Assume that **(H1)** – **(H4)** hold. If*

$$L_g \frac{(T - t_0)^\beta}{\Gamma(\beta + 1)} \left(\theta + c_f \frac{(T - t_0)^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}\right) + \left(p_m + c_g \frac{(T - t_0)^\beta}{\Gamma(\beta + 1)}\right) L_f \frac{(T - t_0)^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} < 1, \quad (13)$$

then the problem (1) has a unique positive bounded below solution.

Proof. Let c_f and c_g are positive real numbers such that,

$$|f(t, x(t))| \leq c_f, \quad |g(t, x(t))| \leq c_g,$$

for any $t \in J$ and $x, y \in \mathcal{C}_\theta$. According to Theorem 3.1, the problem (1) has at least one positive bounded below solution in S . Now, we need only to prove that the product operator $\mathcal{A}\mathcal{B}x$ is a contraction mapping

on X , where \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} are defined as in (5) and (6). Indeed, for any $x, y \in \mathcal{C}_\theta$ and $t \in J$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\mathcal{A}x\mathcal{B}x)(t) - (\mathcal{A}y\mathcal{B}y)(t)| \\
 & \leq \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\beta-1} |g(s, x(s)) - g(s, y(s))| ds \right) \left(\theta + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} f(s, x(s)) ds \right) \\
 & + \left(|p(t)| + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\beta-1} |g(s, y(s))| ds \right) \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_0}^t (t-s)^{\alpha-1} |f(s, x(s)) - f(s, y(s))| ds \right) \\
 & \leq \left(L_g \frac{(t-t_0)^\beta}{\Gamma(\beta+1)} \|x-y\| \right) \left(\theta + c_f \frac{(t-t_0)^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \right) + \left(|p(t)| + c_g \frac{(t-t_0)^\beta}{\Gamma(\beta+1)} \right) \left(L_f \frac{(t-t_0)^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \|x-y\| \right) \\
 & \leq \left(L_g \frac{(T-t_0)^\beta}{\Gamma(\beta+1)} \left(\theta + c_f \frac{(T-t_0)^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \right) + \left(p_m + c_g \frac{(T-t_0)^\beta}{\Gamma(\beta+1)} \right) L_f \frac{(T-t_0)^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \right) \|x-y\|,
 \end{aligned}$$

where $p_m = \max_{t \in J} |p(t)|$. Hence, by (13) the product operator $\mathcal{A}x\mathcal{B}x$ is a contraction mapping. Therefore, the problem (1) has a unique positive bounded below solution $x \in \mathcal{C}_\theta$. \square

5. Monotonicity of positive solutions

Theorem 5.1. *Let p , g and f be non-decreasing functions with respect to both variables, $f(t_0, x(t_0)) \geq 0$ and $g(t_0, x(t_0)) \geq 0$. Moreover, let (H1) – (H4) hold, then there is a monotonic non-decreasing positive bounded below solution of the problem (1).*

Proof. Define a subset $R = \{x \in S : x \text{ is nondecreasing on } J\}$, then R is a closed and convex subset of S . The operator \mathcal{B} is uniformly bounded and completely continuous and the operator \mathcal{A} is Lipschitzian with Lipschitz constant σ , and satisfying $\sigma \sup \{\|\mathcal{B}x\| : x \in R\} \leq 1$. It remains for applying the Dhage theorem that $\mathcal{A}x\mathcal{B}x \in R$ whenever $x, y \in R$. To this end, it suffices to consider $x, y \in R$, $t_1, t_2 \in J$ with $t_1 < t_2$. It follows that

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{A}x(t_2)\mathcal{B}y(t_2) - \mathcal{A}x(t_1)\mathcal{B}y(t_1) \\
 & = \mathcal{A}x(t_2)(\mathcal{B}y(t_2) - \mathcal{B}y(t_1)) + (\mathcal{A}x(t_2) - \mathcal{A}x(t_1))\mathcal{B}y(t_1) \\
 & = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(p(t_2) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_{t_0}^{t_2} (t_2-s)^{\beta-1} g(s, x(s)) ds \right) \\
 & \times \left(\int_{t_0}^{t_1} ((t_2-s)^{\alpha-1} - (t_1-s)^{\alpha-1}) f(s, y(s)) ds + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} (t_2-s)^{\alpha-1} f(s, y(s)) ds \right) \\
 & + \left(p(t_2) - p(t_1) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_{t_0}^{t_1} ((t_2-s)^{\beta-1} - (t_1-s)^{\beta-1}) g(s, x(s)) ds \right) \\
 & + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_{t_1}^{t_2} (t_2-s)^{\beta-1} g(s, x(s)) ds \left(\theta + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_0}^{t_1} (t_1-s)^{\alpha-1} f(s, y(s)) ds \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

Since $(t_2 - s)^{\alpha-1} - (t_1 - s)^{\alpha-1} < 0$ and $(t_2 - s)^{\beta-1} - (t_1 - s)^{\beta-1} < 0$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{A}x(t_2)\mathcal{B}y(t_2) - \mathcal{A}x(t_1)\mathcal{B}y(t_1) \\
 & \geq \frac{f(t_1, y(t_1))}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \left(p(t_2) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_{t_0}^{t_2} (t_2 - s)^{\beta-1} g(s, x(s)) ds \right) \\
 & \times \left(\int_{t_0}^{t_1} \left((t_2 - s)^{\alpha-1} - (t_1 - s)^{\alpha-1} \right) ds + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} (t_2 - s)^{\alpha-1} ds \right) \\
 & + \left(p(t_2) - p(t_1) + \frac{g(t_1, x(t_1))}{\Gamma(\beta)} \left(\int_{t_0}^{t_1} \left((t_2 - s)^{\alpha-1} - (t_1 - s)^{\alpha-1} \right) ds \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} (t_2 - s)^{\alpha-1} ds \right) \right) \left(\theta + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_0}^{t_1} (t_1 - s)^{\alpha-1} f(s, y(s)) ds \right) \\
 & \geq \frac{f(t_1, y(t_1))}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \left(p(t_2) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_{t_0}^{t_2} (t_2 - s)^{\beta-1} g(s, x(s)) ds \right) ((t_2 - t_0)^\alpha - (t_1 - t_0)^\alpha) \\
 & + \left(p(t_2) - p(t_1) + \frac{g(t_1, x(t_1))}{\Gamma(\beta+1)} \left((t_2 - t_0)^\beta - (t_1 - t_0)^\beta \right) \right) \left(\theta + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{t_0}^{t_1} (t_1 - s)^{\alpha-1} f(s, y(s)) ds \right) \\
 & \geq 0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, with the Dhage fixed point theorem the product operator $\mathcal{AB} : R \rightarrow R$ has a fixed point with the positivity and monotonicity nondecreasing properties which is a solution of the problem (1). \square

Remark 5.1. *The results of Theorem 5.1 are valid in Corollaries 3.1-3.4 if the assumptions of Theorem 5.1 are added to Corollaries 3.1-3.4.*

6. Examples

Example 6.1. *Consider the fractional integro-differential equation*

$$\begin{cases} {}^C D^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\frac{x(t)}{\frac{3+4t}{7} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2})} \int_0^t (t-s)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{x(s)+1}{x(s)+2} \right) ds} \right) = \frac{1}{3+t} \left(\frac{tx(t)}{x(t)+2} + 3 \right), & t \in (0, 1], \\ x(0) = 0, \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

where $\alpha = 1/3$, $\beta = 1/2$, $\theta = 0$, $p(t) = \frac{3+4t}{7}$, $f(t, x) = \frac{1}{3+t} \left(\frac{tx}{x+2} + 3 \right)$ and $g(t, x) = \frac{x+1}{x+2}$. Since g is nondecreasing on x ,

$$\frac{1}{2} \leq g(t, x) \leq 1 \text{ and } \frac{3}{4} \leq f(t, x) \leq 1 \text{ for } t \in [0, 1], x \in [0, +\infty),$$

and

$$L_g \frac{(T-t_0)^\beta}{\Gamma(\beta+1)} \left(|\theta| + c_f \frac{(T-t_0)^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \right) \simeq 0.316 < 1.$$

Then, by Corollary 3.1, (14) has a positive solution which verifies $x_*(t) \leq x(t) \leq x^*(t)$ where

$$x_*(t) = \left(\frac{3+4t}{7} + \frac{t^{\frac{1}{2}}}{2\Gamma(\frac{3}{2})} \right) \frac{3}{4} \frac{t^{\frac{1}{3}}}{\Gamma(\frac{4}{3})},$$

and

$$x^*(t) = \left(\frac{3+4t}{7} + \frac{t^{\frac{1}{2}}}{\Gamma(\frac{3}{2})} \right) \frac{t^{\frac{1}{3}}}{\Gamma(\frac{4}{3})}.$$

This positive solution is unique due to the condition (13) is satisfied since

$$\begin{aligned} & L_g \frac{(T-t_0)^\beta}{\Gamma(\beta+1)} \left(|\theta| + c_f \frac{(T-t_0)^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \right) + \left(p_m + c_g \frac{(T-t_0)^\beta}{\Gamma(\beta+1)} \right) L_f \frac{(T-t_0)^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \\ & \simeq 0.614 < 1. \end{aligned}$$

The property of non-decreasing of this solution is not valid in spite of $f(t, x) = \frac{1}{3+t} \left(\frac{tx}{x+2} + 3 \right)$.

Example 6.2. Consider the fractional integro-differential equation

$$\begin{cases} {}^c D^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\frac{x(t)}{\frac{2t}{\sqrt{3}} + 2 + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\frac{1}{5})} \int_0^t (t-s)^{-\frac{4}{5}} (2 + \sin(x(s))) ds} \right) = \frac{t}{2} \sin(x(t)), & t \in (0, 1], \\ x(0) = 1, \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

where $\alpha = 2/3$, $\beta = 1/5$, $\theta = 1/2$, $p(t) = \frac{2t}{\sqrt{3}} + 2$, $f(t, x) = \frac{t}{2} \sin x$ and $g(t, x) = 2 + \sin x$ for $t \in [0, 1]$, $x \in [\frac{\pi}{6}, \frac{\pi}{2}]$. Hence, g is nondecreasing on x and

$$0 \leq f(t, x) \leq \frac{1}{2}, \quad \frac{5}{2} \leq g(t, x) \leq 3.$$

Since

$$L_g \frac{(T-t_0)^\beta}{\Gamma(\beta+1)} \left(|\theta| + \frac{c_f (T-t_0)^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \right) \simeq 0.994 < 1.$$

Then, by Corollary 3.1, (15) has a positive solution which verifies $x_*(t) \leq x(t) \leq x^*(t)$ where

$$x_*(t) = \frac{t}{\sqrt{3}} + 1 + \frac{5t^{\frac{1}{5}}}{4\Gamma(\frac{6}{5})},$$

and

$$x^*(t) = \left(\frac{2t}{\sqrt{3}} + 2 + \frac{3t^{\frac{1}{5}}}{\Gamma(\frac{6}{5})} \right) \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{t^{\frac{2}{3}}}{2\Gamma(\frac{5}{3})} \right).$$

We could not guarantee this positive solution is unique due to the condition (13) is not satisfied. The property of non-decreasing of this positive solution is valid since f and g are increasing on $[\frac{\pi}{6}, \frac{\pi}{2}]$ and p is increasing on $[0, 1]$.

7. Conclusion

In this paper, we provided the existence, uniqueness and monotonicity of positive solutions of hybrid nonlinear fractional integro-differential equations. The main tool of this work is the method of upper and lower solutions and the Dhage and Banach fixed point theorems. However, by introducing a new fixed mapping, we get new positivity conditions.

Acknowledgment

The authors are grateful to the referees for their valuable comments which have led to improvement of the presentation.

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